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DEVELOPMENT OF FRAMEWORK FOR DESCRIBING AND CONSTRUCTING FUN EXPERIENCE.

Young Bin Jung / Eui Chul Jung
Yonsei University / Yonsei University
jech@yonsei.ac.kr

ABSTRACT

Nowadays people consider the pleasure of use when choosing products, so understanding the way of how people perceive fun experience is critical to design an interactive product and system. The goal of this research is to develop the framework to describe how people feel fun experience when using interactive products. Netnography and FGI (Focus-Group Interview) methods were used to collect the data of people's fun experience. In order to form a theoretical base, grounded theory is adopted to discover the different stage of fun experience. Through the analyses, users' fun experiences can be categorized with 40 fun elements. The relationship amongst the elements was drawn as well. The framework can be extensively applied to design interactive product in an emotional and enjoyable way in design practice.

Keywords: Framework, Fun experience, User experience

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally product design and development processes have started from the function related needs of users (Ulrich & Eppinger, 2008), and HCI has been concerned with how task can be achieved with less operation. However, nowadays most products meet the functional requirements due to the elevation of technical standards, people start to care not the effectiveness of use, but the pleasure of use when purchasing the product. Therefore usability issues in HCI have been moved from useful and efficient towards emotional concerns. One reason for the slow adoption of fun and enjoyment as a research topic in the HCI community

is surely the subjectivity of enjoyment (Monk et al., 2002). HCI researchers tend to focus on observations of behavior and objective measurement. In general, they are suspicious about the introspective and personal judgments of users because user's needs and opinions seem to be too fuzzy, contradictive, irrational, and non-predictive to seriously ground design decisions. In other words, it is difficult to ensure objectivity of the process how people perceive fun experience based on personal and subjective interpretation. For this reason, empirical approaches are required to capture emotional and pleasant factors that arouse fun experience. In order to incorporate fun factors into product and system design, the mechanism of what factors make people pleasant and how people feel enjoyable. People's experiential emotion has been changing continuously because of the development of new functionality and interactive technique in new media. Exploring the mechanism of experiencing fun should be the start point for interactive product and system designers. To gain pleasurable experiences while interacting with products, three levels of skill's have to be considered; cognitive skills, perceptual-motor skills and emotional skills. In other words: knowing, doing and feeling; the wholly trinity of interaction (Blythe, 2003).

This research accordingly aims 1) to define fun elements, 2) to categorize the elements by meaning and/or stages of experiencing fun, and 3) to discover how the elements work and are inter-related each other in terms of the cognitive flow of fun experience. The results of this research will provide interactive researchers and designers with theoretical and user-oriented foundations for designing products and systems in an emotional and enjoyable way.

GOAL & METHOD

The goal of this research is to establish the framework for describing and constructing fun experience while using interactive products and contents. The framework suggested in this research will be utilized 1) to understand and describe why and how people form fun experience and 2) to construct fun experience strategically for designing products and contents in an emotional way. First of all, previous publications have been reviewed. Several similar frameworks such as the PLEX have been suggested to define playful experience (Arrasvuori, 2010). However, users' fun experience has been changing and extending continuously because of new emerging interactive technology. In order to establish the new framework, netnography method which is applied version of ethnography for analyzing users' behaviors and opinions in the internet world (Kozinets, 2002). Internet is not just a tool to serve as channels of communications and as a marketplace of buying and selling goods. Netnography method assumes that internet is another independent society which has and forms own social and cultural context through seamless interaction with the real world. Due to anonymous attribute of internet, many realistic and unaffected data regarding fun experience can be collected without any intervention of interviewers and/or researchers. For this research, diverse users' fun experience has been collected from users' postings on the famous web-sites on interactive digital artifacts and contents. Along with the netnography method, FGI (Focus-Group Interview) was conducted to collect fun experience from different user groups. Many stories on fun experience of using many interactive products and contents such as game consoles, MP3 players, mobile phones, game software, web-sites, and media arts have been investigated for this research. For extracting mechanism of forming fun experience from the empirical data, several qualitative research methods were initially investigated to form a theoretical base. Grounded theoretical method was used for this analysis because grounded theory provided the basic framework of analysis in decomposing and reorganizing the interview data. It has been extensively used in various social science fields. Strauss and Corbin define "the grounded

theory approach is a qualitative research method that uses a systematic set of procedures to develop an inductively derived theory about a phenomenon (Strauss, et al., 1987)." Especially, Strauss provides detailed procedures and guidelines for applying the theory to data collection, analysis and theory generation in real analytical practice (Strauss, et al., 1990).

REVIEWS ON DEFINING FUN EXPERIENCE

The early stage of theoretical researches on fun experiences were conducted based on philosophical, psychological, and game-design-based approaches. The *pleasure framework* is a good example and it were compiled framework from previous six publications by Groos (1901), Cailliois (1962), Csikszentmihalyi (1975), Apter (1991), Hunicke, et al.(2004), and Garneau (2001). Thirteen pleasure categories of play were summarized as follow: Creation, Exploration, Discovery, Difficulty, Competition, Danger, Captivation, Sensation, Sympathy, Simulation, Fansasy, Camaraderie, and Subversion (Costello & Edmonds, 2007). The framework by Costello and Edmonds is the initial framework of conceptual development for categorizing playful experience, but the framework focused on evaluating criteria for pleasurable interface in interactive artworks.

Korhonen suggested another framework by introducing the concept of experience instead of pleasurable based on the initial framework by Costello & Edmonds. The reason why he suggested new framework was that the previous one was not extensive enough to explain playful experience because the thirteen pleasure categories only valid for the situation of playing with interactive artwork (Korhonen, et al., 2009). For this reason, three categories of 'Creation,' 'Camaraderie,' and 'Danger' were changed to 'Expression,' 'Fellowship,' and 'Thrill' respectively. The five more categories - 'Control,' 'Nurture,' 'Completion,' 'Sadism,' and 'Suffering' - were added as well. The initial PLEX (Playful Experience) model was suggested by adding 'Relaxation' and 'Eroticism' from the analysis of the interview with thirteen game players. (Korhonen, et al., 2009).

After that, Korhonen had conducted additional researches with twenty-one participants using diary

analysis. The participants were asked to record their own playful experiences of using personal products (e.g., mobile phones, portable music players and fitness products) for ten days. As a result, two more categories - 'Humor' and 'Submission' - were added and the final PLEX was completed with twenty-two categories as shown in table 1 (Korhonen, et al., 2010).

Experience category	Brief description: the Playful Experience emerges from...
Captivation	Forgetting one's surroundings
Challenge	Testing abilities in a demanding task
Competition	Contest with oneself or an opponent
Completion	Finishing a major task or reaching closure
Control	Dominating, commanding or regulating
Cruelty	Causing mental or physical pain
Discovery	Finding something new or unknown
Eroticism	A sexually arousing situation
Exploration	Investigating an object or situation
Expression	Expression Manifesting oneself creatively
Fantasy	An imagined situation
Fellowship	Friendship, communality or intimacy
Humor	Fun, joy, amusement, jokes or gags
Nurture	Taking care of oneself or others
Relaxation	Relief from bodily or mental work
Sensation	Excitement by stimulating senses
Simulation	An imitation of everyday life
Submission	Being part of a larger structure
Subversion	Breaking social rules and norms
Suffering	Loss, frustration or anger
Sympathy	Sharing emotional feelings
Thrill	Excitement derived from risk or Danger

Table 1. Fun Categories in PLEX

However, fun experience is getting extended more and more because new functionality and interaction techniques such as touch-based operation and augmented reality have been introduced continuously. This means the meaning of fun experience is expanding and new fun elements are emerging simultaneously.

Moreover, from the Korhonen' research using 10 days diary analysis, three categories - 'Cruelty,' 'Eroticism,' and 'Challenge' were missed because these categories are obvious while interacting between a human and virtual counterparts in the network environment rather than between a use and a product (Korhonen, et al., 2010).

This means new discovery of fun elements is required in such a socially networked environment. SNS (Social Network System) such as Facebook and Twitter forms new emotional effect. These emergent fun experiences are needed to be investigated to come up with the emotional changes of people.

REVIEWS ON CONSTRUCTING FUN EXPERIENCE

Along with capturing fun elements, the flow of forming fun experience should be discovered in order to design interaction in a pleasant way. Product experience consists of three levels: aesthetic experience, experience of meaning, and emotional response (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). Aesthetic experience is a sensory modality which is formed through human's perceptual system such as look, sound, touch, and smell from target objects.

Attribution of meaning is a part of cognitive process which is a result of semantic interpretation and assess of target objects. Emotional experience is an emotional result through evaluation from events in a certain situation. Satisfaction and dissatisfaction are examples of emotional experience.

Assume a situation that a user is about to use a new teacup purchased in China. He or she may enjoy hearing the sound produced by the fragile porcelain lid when it is placed on the top. It is a stage of aesthetic experience. He or she may consider the teacup as a memento that represents his visit to china. It can come into the stage of experience of meaning. Finally, as a result of cognitive process, the teacup produces emotional satisfaction while using the teacup. It is the stage of emotional response. The PLEX suggest another three level category in terms of product experience (e.g., Aesthetic pleasure : Sensation, Expression, Attribution of meaning : Simulation, Completion, Fansasy, Emotional response : Thrill, Sympathy).

However, the PLEX do not describe relationships amongst fun categories in the three levels of product experience. Investigating cause-effect relationships between each fun element is important for designing UI of interactive products that make people feel fun experience. That is because embedding the flow of forming fun experiences in designing is critical in order to form accurate perception of fun experience when people interacting with interactive products.

CAPTURING FUN ELEMENTS

To capture fun elements that make people feel fun experience, users' comments on several digital artifacts on internet sites have been collected. Some examples of collected fun-related data are as follows: '... I love to challenge new mission...' , '... I

can learn how to cook a specific food as playing a game ... ,’ and ‘... I want to break a record posted on Facebook’ These individual postings contain fun elements that arouse fun experience. FGI method is also used to capture users’ fun experience. Twenty three interviewees were participated in the discussion, and the interviewees are divided into two sub-groups. Twelve interviewees are general user group who utilize default and general features in products. Other eleven interviewees are expert user group who are a kind of early adaptors and/or lead users. Each sub-group is divided into three sub groups by their preferences of using digital products and contents as shown in Table 2. During the data gathering on diverse internet sites, the fun elements seem to be varied depending on sex, age, and level of expertise. By this reason, six groups were sophisticatedly recruited and each group has different level and preference of utilizing digital products and contents. Basic questions in proceeding scenarios are as follows: 1) which digital devices (or media) do you prefer, 2) which contents (or features) do you take pleasure, and 3) When and how do you feel fun.

General User Group			Expert User Group		
Women	20-30	Over 40	Women	20-30	Over 40
4	4	4	4	4	3

Table 2. Interviewee Selection Matrix

GROUNDING THEORY

In order to analyze the capture data and structure theoretical basis, grounded theory is adopted in this research. The essential procedures of grounded theoretical data analysis include coding data with focus on key elements and generating categories by relating those elements. Data coding techniques include three overlapping processes in his proposed methods: open coding, axial coding, and selective coding. The aim of open coding is to break data and produce totally tentative concepts and their dimensions from the data. Axial coding consists of intensive analysis to revolve around one category at a time, refining and developing categories. During selective coding, researchers limit the coding to core codes-related codes. These data coding and categorization techniques were partially applied

throughout this research to decompose and reconfigure the interview data.

OPEN CODING: EXTRACTING FUN ELEMENTS

Open coding was used to extract concept of fun elements. The process of extracting fun elements are as follows, after 1) in-vivo codes were drawn, then 2) a concept in the codes are selected and grouped, then 3) a provisional name was given, and 4) the category name related to multiple provisional names was created.

In-vivo code	Concept	Provisional Name	Category
... can save phone number automatically usefulness of features to my schedule ...	Feature close to life	Novelty
... can enlarge part of screen to see details hidden functions ...	Unexpected Feature	
... can navigate map as I drag full touch LCD ...	Re-recognized usefulness of existing feature	

Table 3. Examples of Open Coding for ‘Novelty’ Category

Table 3 show an examples of how the category (fun elements) of ‘Novelty’ are grounded extracted from users’ statements from internet sites and FGI. By following this process forty fun elements were drawn in this research as shown in table 4.

Fun Category (Elements)	Brief Description
User Goal & Motivation	Intention, Want to do
User Involvement	Degree of control
Challenge	Attitude
Skill	Degree of ability
Familiarity	Frequently used Features
Metaphor	Appropriate symbol
Relevance	Appropriateness in a certain situation
Trendiness	How match to current trend
Showing Off	Ostentation
Aesthetic Quality	Shape, Graphic quality
Unexpectedness	Interesting hidden features
Finding & Learning	Discover new value
Good Feeling	Positive emotion before use

Novelty	Positive emotion after use, Unique
Interest & Curiosity	Trigger more interests
Problem Solving	Process of finding solutions
Physical Familiarity	Use something in a similar way in the real world
Social Metaphor	Social connotation
Personal Preference	Personal necessities
Intimacy	Rapport with others
Achievement	Satisfaction when complete something
Sensitivity of System Setting	Control the system as I want to do
Vividness	Clearness of outputs
Response Time & Speediness	Prompt response
Multi-Channel Experience (Output)	Diverse outputs using sound, lights, etc.
Multi-Channel Operation (Input)	Diverse inputs using touch, behaviors, etc.
Mapping	Appropriate mapping between user behaviors and system reactions
Personalization & Customization	Modify something only for a specific user
Do It Yourself	Create something that is not delivered by manufacturers
Degree of Freedom	Diverse options, multiple choices
Self-Expression	Show personal emotion, status
Participation	Sympathy
Collaboration	Fellowship, Do together to achieve something
Competition	Rivalry
Storytelling	Hidden story, Legend
Realistic Representation	Sophisticatedly represented
Fruit & Reward	Compensation for good results
Concentration	Absorption in doing something
Time Distortion	Cannot recognize time lapse
Frequency of Use	Increase use time
Exploration	Take a journey for new features

Table 4. Forty Fun Categories (Elements)

To develop a practical guideline for designers who want to embed the concept in table 4, the reference manual is developed with the format as shown in Table 5. The bold typed text represents fun element. The description of each fun element and some representative examples are followed. This manual

will inspire designers when they should consider fun factors in designing.

Multi-Channel Operation (Input)	
A user can operate and control products and systems with diverse input methods (e.g. touching, clicking, voice-commanding)	
Wii	
Users' behavior itself is the input methods. User can control it as they move.	

Table 5. One example in Reference Manual

AXIAL CODING: INTERRELATING FUN ELEMENTS

Categorize elements into paradigm is the next step to develop a framework to describe how user's fun experience has been formed while using the interactive products and systems. In grounded theory, the concept of six paradigms - causal conditions, context, phenomena, intervening conditions, action/interaction, and consequences - used to show the flow how a specific social and/or cultural phenomenon.

Figure 1. Flow of Forming Fun Experience

In this research, the axial coding scheme is adopted to reveal the flow how people' fun experience is formed as shown in Figure 1. This model also shows cause-effect relations and flow among the fun elements of forming fun experience.

SELECTIVE CODING: FINDING STRATEGIC FLOW

When developing interactive products and systems, designers usually want to provide optimized solutions for design problems. In other words, many designers want to guide customers to use something in an intended way by designers.

If patterns of flow for a specific fun experience are revealed, it is easier to design interactive products that arouse specific fun results. The selective coding is conducted to reveal frequently associated relations by clustering intimate and close fun elements frequently found during the research. These patterns are significant to design and develop interactive products in design practice.

Figure 2. Example of Strategic Patterns

Figure 2 demonstrate that the framework in Figure 1 can be used to analyze why people feel fun when they navigating the specific website, the HONDA website. User's mental process sets on the X axis and stages of use (Before Use, While Use, and After Use) set on the Y axis. The analysis is conducted by applying forty fun elements, so the process of fun experience can be described in more systemic and logical ways. Through this analysis with other cases, some patterns are summarized as follows: 1) novelty > multi-channel experience/operation > exploration, 2) aesthetic quality > vividness > concentration, 3) finding & learning > do it yourself > exploration, and so on.

This framework also used for developing design strategy. Figure 3 shows a good example of design strategy for designing mobile phone features that make people feel fun. This figure is drawn by interviews. The main questionnaires were what factors make you engaged and annoyed in the use of mobile phones when you buy it and while you are using it. Through the analysis, a strategic map can be suggested as shown in Figure 3. The map shows which fun factors in each feature must be considered carefully when designing a mobile phone for arousing fun experience. The feature in a mobile phone is deployed along the circle and relevant fun elements are deployed on each onion-shell-shaped circle. The size of each circles plotted inside the map represent the importance of fun factors in a specific feature. For example, people consider 'Newness (Novelty)' and 'Vividness' in idle screen important, so mobile phone designers must generate concepts that fun can trigger fun experience. By referring to description of fun elements manual in Table 5, designers can develop concepts in more systemic ways.

Figure 3. Strategic Map for Designing Mobile Phone

CONCLUSION

This research suggests the framework with forty fun elements and the relationships amongst the elements. In addition, frequently perceived patterns of fun experience are drawn. The collections of these patterns call strategic fun flows can be utilized to

make user feel specific fun experience when designing interaction.

The framework suggested in this research can be used for analyzing why and how people feel fun, and for planning how to develop contents and services that make people feel fun. Satisfying emotional aspects becomes more and more important in the future. In this sense, the framework can be used fundamentally and practically for designing artefacts and contents that can appeal emotional aspects. For the further research, the framework should be refined elaborately to explain the details of cause-effect relations with individual fun elements and verify the strategic and dominant fun flows since it is still at the hypothetical level.

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